

A STATISTICAL STUDY ON OBESITY AND ITS IMPACT ON HUMAN HEALTH

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Abstract: After the questionnaire forms were distributed to a sample of the community (males and females) which amounted to (50) samples, we entered the answers and sorted them through the statistical program (SPSS) and obtained several conclusions that we summarize in several points as follows:

- A percentage (0.016) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), and this means that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena of gender and thyroid gland secretion on weight, as shown in Table No. (4).
- A percentage (40.00) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), and this means that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena of academic achievement and obesity leading to joint, skeletal and muscular problems, as shown in Table No. (5).
- A percentage of (0.007) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), which means that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena of academic achievement and absence or lack of exercise, as shown in Table No. (6).
- A percentage of (0.006) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), which means that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena of suffering from obesity and the belief that childhood obesity means lifelong obesity, as shown in Table No. (7).

- A percentage of (0.046) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), which means that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena of suffering from obesity and having diabetes as one of the harms of marital obesity, as shown in Table No. (8).

Introduction:

Obesity is a common and widespread disease around the world. It is a disease that spreads among children and adults, both males and females. Recently, obesity has become a serious health problem that requires treatment and follow-up due to the fact that it causes many diseases and health problems.

The definition of an obese person is a person who has excess fatty tissue and a body mass index value higher than 30. The body mass index is an index that measures weight compared to height, as excess fatty tissue may have serious health consequences. It is a very large source of diseases that the body may suffer from. It may suffer from joint pain, reaching the point of the person being unable to walk, due to the excess body load.

It also causes many heart and lung diseases, gallbladder diseases, and high blood pressure, and causes an increase in the percentage of cholesterol in the body, which the person cannot control, and from the least food it may cause the inability to breathe, and difficulty walking.

Obesity is one of the most common medical conditions in Western society today and one of the most difficult to treat and address. Relatively little progress has been made in the treatment of obesity other than lifestyle changes, but much information has been gathered regarding the medical consequences of obesity. Obesity is usually caused by genetic, physiological, and environmental factors, as well as dietary choices, physical activity, and exercise. The good news is that even a small amount of weight loss can improve or prevent health problems associated with obesity. A healthier diet, increased physical activity, and behavioral changes can help with weight loss. Prescription medications and surgical weight-loss procedures are also possible options for treating obesity.

First: The importance of the research.

The importance of the research lies in shedding light on the phenomenon of obesity and contributing to finding solutions to reduce the exacerbation of this phenomenon by practicing healthier eating habits to treat obesity, and because this topic is one of the important topics due to its impact on human mental health.

Second: The research problem:

Obesity is one of the most common problems that people suffer from in the current era, and it is one of the most dangerous problems that affect humans; Rather, it is a medical problem that increases the risk factors for diseases and other health problems such as heart disease, diabetes, high blood pressure and certain types of cancer. As a result, it is necessary to identify the causes that influence the increase in obesity due to its many and disturbing harms. It affects the psychological health, mental health, and physical health of humans.

Third: The aim of the research

The aim of the research lies in :

1. Identify the causes of obesity and ways to treat it.
2. Also identify the effects of obesity on humans.

Fourth: Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were relied upon in formulating the research:

There is no relationship between the variables: H₀

There is a relationship between the variables: H₁

Fifth: Research community and sample

The students of the Institute of Management were chosen as the study community due to the ease of obtaining data and ensuring the accuracy of answering the research questions. A sample of 50 students from the Department of Statistics Technology was chosen.

Sixth: Research methodology:

There are many methods that can be relied upon in the subject of our research, including traditional methods, such as: the historical method, and the comparative method. And contemporary methods, such as: the analytical method, and the statistical method. Therefore, according to this research, we will use the analytical and statistical method; for the purpose of explaining and analyzing the causes leading to obesity.

Seventh: Method of collecting samples

The research relied on designing a questionnaire that reflected the factors that lead to obesity and the factors contributing to the incidence of diseases resulting from obesity and some preventive measures to reduce the risk of infection. It was distributed to the sample members, numbering (50) students.

Eighth: Statistical methods

Statistical processing was carried out using the ready-made program (SPSS) to extract and analyze the final results. The independence test, Chi-square test, was relied upon.

Obesity and its impact on human health:

Obesity is a global phenomenon that has received the attention of many researchers in many fields, especially healthcare specialists, due to its relationship with a variety of medical physical problems. The World Health Organization has called it the "deadly poison" because it is the cause of many fatal diseases, about 48 serious diseases such as diabetes, heart and arterial diseases, some types of cancer, arthritis, digestive and respiratory problems, infertility, and because of its negative impact on a person's psychological state and social life. Many scientists have talked about the effects of obesity and have allocated it to women more than men, and the body weight of each of us is a relative matter governed by age, height, and gender. The problem of obesity is not just heavy weight, but rather a fundamental problem that carries within it what is more dangerous than that.

The harms and diseases caused by obesity:

Sleep apnea: Obesity increases the risk of developing sleep apnea; It is a condition in which breathing stops momentarily during sleep. Obesity causes the airways to contract and hinders their expansion due to the presence of large amounts of fat stored around the neck, which results in difficulty breathing during sleep and possibly the appearance of snoring.

Liver diseases: Obesity increases the chances of developing liver diseases, such as fatty liver disease, also known as non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. It is worth noting that the accumulation of fat in the liver may lead to its damage or cirrhosis.

Pregnancy problems: Obesity is a major cause of health problems and complications during pregnancy, including the following:

- Gestational diabetes.
- Preeclampsia; a condition of high blood pressure during pregnancy, and it is noted that its effect may be negatively reflected on the pregnant woman and the fetus.
- The need for a cesarean section during childbirth.

Osteoarthritis: Obesity increases the risk of developing osteoarthritis, the symptoms of which appear as pain and swelling in the affected joint, and limited movement. This is due to the fact that obesity increases the pressure on the joints and bones.

Treatment of Obesity:

1. It is necessary to be careful to go to the doctor to identify the causes of obesity and treat it properly.
2. Do not eat processed foods.
3. Limit the consumption of fats and sugars.
4. Follow diets decided by specialists.
5. Use some medications and herbs that help in losing weight.
6. Treatment with fat-burning drugs may be resorted to under the supervision of a doctor, while being careful to stay away from unlicensed medications.
7. The doctor may resort to surgical intervention when it is not possible to treat with other methods.

There was no significant advantage in the research for one method of treating obesity over another, but there is great importance in educating patients to treat obesity, regarding how to plan the daily menu early, and record the meals that were eaten, as behavioral auditing in the treatment of obesity is the cornerstone of losing weight in the right way.

Prevention of Obesity:

1. It is necessary to be careful to exercise regularly every day to prevent obesity.
2. Avoid stress, anxiety, and psychological and nervous pressure.
3. Avoid eating foods that contain a high percentage of calories, including ready-made foods and soft drinks.
4. Eat healthy food that contains fiber, especially fresh vegetables and fruits.
5. Avoid processed foods.
6. Reduce sugar consumption.

The applied aspect:

First: Chi-square test:

This test shows the existence or absence of a relationship between two phenomena or variables, as there is a null hypothesis (H_0) and an alternative hypothesis (H_1) that was adopted within a significance level (99% and 95%), using the statistical program SPSS v.20:

Chi-Square Test of Independence:

Chi-Square test of independence is a simple test to find out whether there is a relationship between two variables. This test is conducted by comparing a value determined by the researcher in advance, known as the significance level (α), with the value called p-Value, which is calculated from the available data, as

it will become clear by comparing the two values whether there is a relationship between the variables or not.

1-Formulating hypotheses: Null hypothesis and alternative hypothesis

The first hypothesis is the null hypothesis:

There is no relationship between the two variables and this hypothesis is symbolized by H_0 , which is assumed to be true when testing two variables. The hypothesis is written in this way:

V_1 is independent of V_2 . Where 1 and 2 are the variables under study. In English, the statistical null hypothesis is written in the following form :

H_0 : V_1 is independent of V_2 (no relationship between the two variables)

The second hypothesis is the alternative hypothesis:

There is a relationship between the two variables under study and this hypothesis is symbolized by H_1 . It is written in the following way:

V_1 is not independent or dependent on V_2 . Where 1 and 2 are the variables under study. In English, the alternative hypothesis is written as follows:

H_1 : V_1 is dependent on V_2 (there is a relationship between the two variables)

2-Level of Significance (Alpha)

When conducting a chi-square test, the researcher must choose a value called Level of Significance or Level of Significance (Alpha), which is represented by the symbol (α). This value can be said to represent the probability of making an error in the test called a type I error, which is rejecting the null hypothesis H_0 even though it is correct. In other words, the researcher concludes based on the available data that there is a relationship between the two variables even though there is no relationship, which is a wrong conclusion.

This value determined by the researcher is compared to a value called p-value, which can be calculated manually or using one of the famous statistical programs from the data collected by the researcher. The value of alpha or Level of Significance is often used as 0.01 or 0.05, and the choice is up to the researcher and the extent of the error range that he wants to allow, where in the case of choosing $\alpha = 0.01$, the test result is more accurate.

3- What is the P-Value and what does it mean?

The P-Value can be referred to as a measure to clarify the extent to which we have evidence or proof to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_1) in the test we have.

In other words, the lower the P-Value, the stronger the evidence or proof we have against the validity of the null hypothesis or accepting the null hypothesis, and therefore, the lower the value, the more inclined we are to accept the alternative hypothesis.

4- Comparing the result with the level of significance chosen by the researcher The next step when interpreting the result is to compare some values.

If the researcher chooses the level of significance or $\alpha = 0.01$, we compare the values of the level of significance and the P-Value that we obtained from the test as follows:

➤ If the value of (P-Value) is greater than the value of the level of significance, which is 0.01

Based on the value of the chi-square test for independence, it can be said that there is sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis, and therefore, it can be said that the two variables under study are independent and one does not affect the other.

➤ If the value of (P-Value) is less than the value of the significance level, which is 0.01

Based on the value of the Chi-square test for independence, it can be said that there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, and thus it can be said that the two variables under study are not independent and one affects the other, and in the same way, a comparison can be made between the two values if the researcher chooses another significance level value

When we choose a significance level of 0.01, we are sure of the accuracy of the test by 99%

However, often in studies that do not require very high accuracy, the researcher chooses another significance level, such as 0.05, and thus, when obtaining the test value and the result, it can be said that the result is correct by 95%

Second: - Analysis of research data

In order to achieve the objectives of the research, the researchers used the descriptive analytical method for the purpose of a statistical study on obesity and its effect on human health.

The necessary data was obtained through the questionnaire that was prepared for this purpose, and the data was unloaded and the results were analyzed using the SPSS statistical program.

First: General information about the research sample:

Table No. (1) shows the distribution of the research sample members according to the gender variable.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	22	44	44	44
	Female	28	56	56	100.0
	Total	50.0	100.0	100.0	

It is clear from Table No. (1) that the distribution of the sample according to gender showed that (22) respondents, representing (44%), were males, while the remaining responses, representing (56%), were females.

Table No. (2) shows the distribution of the research sample members according to the age variable.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Less than 20	9	18	18	18
	21_30	31	62	62	80
	31_40	5	10	10	90
	41_50	5	10	10	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Table No. (2) shows the respondents according to the age group level, where the first group represented (9%), the second group represented (31%), the third group represented (5%), and the last group represented (5%).

Table No. (3) shows the distribution of the research sample members according to the variable of academic achievement.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Read and write	4	18	18	8
	Preparatory or less diploma	17	34	34	42
	Bachelor's	26	52	52	94
	Total	3	16	16	100
	Total	50.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Table No. (3) shows that the distribution of the sample according to educational attainment showed that (4) respondents, representing (18%), read and write, and 34% of those with a preparatory certificate or less, and the largest percentage, 52%, were diploma holders, while the remaining responses represented (16%) of those with a bachelor's degree.

Second: - The tables in which the data were analyzed using Chi-Square to choose the relationship between the variables to accept and reject the null and alternative hypothesis.

Table No. (4) shows the relationship between gender and the effect of thyroid gland secretion on weight

Crosstab					
Count					
		Does thyroid gland secretion affect weight?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	
Gender	Male	13	1	8	22
	Female	26	0	2	28
Total		39	1	10	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.333 ^a	2	.016
Likelihood Ratio	8.937	2	.011
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.443	1	.006
N of Valid Cases	50		
a. 3 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .44.			

Hypothesis

- There is no significant relationship between gender and thyroid secretion on weight: H0
- There is a significant relationship between gender and thyroid secretion on weight: H1

It is clear from Table No. (4) that the Chi-Square value reached (0.016) which is less than the significance level (0.05) and therefore we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis

Table No. (5) shows the relationship between academic achievement and obesity leading to joint, skeletal and muscular problems

Crosstab						
Count						
		Age group				Total
		Yes	To some extent	No	41_50	
Academic achievement	Read and write	2	2	0	0	4
	Preparatory	8	8	1	3	17
	Bachelor's	2	21	2	1	26
	Postgraduate	0	0	2	1	3

	studies					
Total		9	31	5	5	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	24.095 ^a	9	.004
Likelihood Ratio	20.814	9	.014
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.176	1	.041
N of Valid Cases	50		

a. 14 cells (87.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .30.

Hypothesis

H0

- There is no significant relationship between academic achievement and obesity leading to joint, skeletal and muscular problems

H1 - There is a significant relationship between academic achievement and obesity leading to joint, skeletal and muscular problems

It is clear from Table No. (5) that the Chi-Square value reached (0.004) which is less than the significance level (0.05) and accordingly we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis

Table No. (6) shows the relationship between academic achievement and the absence or lack of exercise leads to obesity

Crosstab					
Count					
		Does lack of exercise lead to obesity?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	
Academic achievement	Read and write	2	2	0	4
	Preparatory	9	0	8	17
	Bachelor's	18	1	7	26
	Postgraduate studies	2	0	1	3
Total		31	3	16	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	17.551 ^a	6	.007
Likelihood Ratio	11.983	6	.062
Linear-by-Linear Association	.296	1	.586
N of Valid Cases	50		

a. 8 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

Hypothesis

There is no relationship between academic achievement and absence or lack of exercise: H0

-There is a relationship between academic achievement and absence or lack of exercise: H1

It is clear to us from Table No. (6) that the value of Chi-Square reached (0.007) which is less than the significance level (0.05) and accordingly we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, i.e. there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena

Table No. (7) shows the relationship between suffering from obesity and the belief that obesity in childhood means obesity for life

Crosstab					
Count					
		Do you think childhood obesity means lifelong obesity?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	
Are you obese?	Yes	2	3	1	6
	No	25	1	8	34
	To some extent	10	0	0	10
Total		37	1	12	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	18.270 ^a	6	.006
Likelihood Ratio	9.520	6	.146
Linear-by-Linear Association	.003	1	.954
N of Valid Cases	50		

a. 9 cells (75.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .06.

Hypothesis

H0: - There is no significant relationship between suffering from obesity and the belief that childhood obesity means obesity for life

H1: - There is a significant relationship between suffering from obesity and the belief that childhood obesity means obesity for life

It is clear to us from Table No. (7) that the Chi-Square value reached (0.006) which is less than the significance level (0.05) and accordingly we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis

Table No. (8) shows the relationship between suffering from obesity and that diabetes is one of the harms of obesity

Crosstab					
Count					
		Do you think that diabetes is one of the harms of obesity?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	
Are you obese?	Yes	2	0	4	6
	No				

	No	25	1	8	34
	To some extent	10	0	0	10
Total		37	1	12	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.680 ^a	4	.046
Likelihood Ratio	11.141	4	.025
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.562	1	.003
N of Valid Cases	50		

a. 6 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

Hypothesis

H0: -There is no significant relationship between suffering from obesity and diabetes as one of the harms of obesity

H1: -There is a significant relationship between suffering from obesity and diabetes as one of the harms of obesity

It is clear to us from Table No. (8) that the Chi-Square value reached (0.046) which is less than the significance level (0.05) and accordingly we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis

Table No. (9) shows the relationship between the obese person being exposed to a number of serious health problems and the absence or lack of exercise leading to obesity

Crosstab					
Count					
		Does lack of exercise lead to obesity?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	
Is an obese person at risk for a number of serious health problems?	Yes	25	1	11	37
	No	2	2	1	5
	To some extent	4	0	4	8
Total		31	3	16	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.639 ^a	4	.013
Likelihood Ratio	7.831	4	.098
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.149	1	.284
N of Valid Cases	50		

a. 7 cells (77.8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .30.

Hypothesis

H0: -There is no significant relationship between the obese person being exposed to a number of serious health problems and the absence or lack of exercise leading to obesity

H1: -There is a significant relationship between the obese person being exposed to a number of serious health problems and the absence or lack of exercise leading to obesity

It is clear to us from Table No. (9) that the Chi-Square value reached (0.013) which is less than the significance level (0.05) and accordingly we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis

Table No. (10) shows the relationship between the obese person being exposed to a number of serious health problems and the frequent consumption of foods, sugars and starches leading to obesity

Crosstab					
Count					
		Does eating a lot of processed foods, sugars and starches lead to obesity?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	
Is an obese person at risk for a number of serious health problems?	Yes	30	0	7	37
	No	3	1	1	5
	To some extent	4	0	4	8
Total		37	1	12	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.691 ^a	4	.013
Likelihood Ratio	7.870	4	.096
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.442	1	.064
N of Valid Cases	50		

a. 6 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .10.

Hypothesis

H0: - There is no significant relationship between serious health problems and frequent consumption of processed foods, sugars and starches on obesity

H1: - There is a significant relationship between serious health problems and frequent consumption of processed foods, sugars and starches on obesity

It is clear from Table No. (10) that the Chi-Square value reached (0.013) which is less than the significance level (0.05) and accordingly we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis

Table No. (11) shows the relationship between eating healthy food, one of the most important ways to prevent obesity, and the effect of thyroid secretion on weight

Crosstab					
Count					
		Does thyroid gland secretion affect weight?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	

Is eating healthy food one of the most important ways to prevent obesity?	Yes	29	0	7	36
	No	1	1	1	3
	To some extent	9	0	2	11
Total		39	1	10	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	16.775 ^a	4	.002
Likelihood Ratio	6.903	4	.141
Linear-by-Linear Association	.011	1	.916
N of Valid Cases	50		

a. 6 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .06.

Hypothesis

There is a significant relationship between eating healthy food and thyroid secretion on weight: H₀

➤ There is a significant relationship between eating healthy food and thyroid secretion on weight: H₁

It is clear to us from Table No. (11) that the Chi-Square value reached (0.002) which is less than the significance level (0.05) and accordingly we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis

Table No. (12) shows the relationship between

The genetic factor is one of the most important causes that cause obesity in humans and lack of sleep can have a negative effect on body weight

Crosstab					
Count					
		Can lack of sleep have a negative effect on body weight?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	
Do you think that genetic factors are one of the most important causes of obesity in humans?	Yes	7	9	8	24
	No	2	3	2	7
	To some extent	9	0	10	19
Total		18	12	20	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.773 ^a	4	.044
Likelihood Ratio	13.806	4	.008
Linear-by-Linear Association	.001	1	.972
N of Valid Cases	50		

a. 4 cells (44.4%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.68.

Hypothesis

- There is no significant relationship between the genetic factor causing obesity and lack of sleep on weight: H₀
- There is a significant relationship between the genetic factor causing obesity and lack of sleep on weight: H₁

It is clear to us from Table No. (12) that the value of Chi-Square reached (0.044) which is less than the significance level (0.05) and accordingly we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis

Table No. (13) shows the relationship between obesity having an effect on a person's psychological state and social life and that the obese person is exposed to a number of health problems

Crosstab					
Count					
		Is obesity exposed to a number of health problems?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	
Does obesity affect a person's psychological state and social life?	Yes	4	3	13	20
	No	10	5	3	18
	To some extent	4	4	4	12
Total		18	12	20	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.284 ^a	4	.036
Likelihood Ratio	10.541	4	.032
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.169	1	.075
N of Valid Cases	50		

a. 5 cells (55.6%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.88.

Hypothesis

H₀: -There is no significant relationship between the fact that obesity has an impact on a person's psychological state and social life and that the obese person is exposed to a number of health problems

H₁: -There is no significant relationship between the fact that obesity has an impact on a person's psychological state and social life and that the obese person is exposed to a number of health problems

It is clear to us from Table No. (13) that the Chi-Square value reached (0.036) which is less than the significance level (0.05) and accordingly we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis

Table No. (14) shows the relationship between the effect of thyroid gland secretion on weight and taking some medications leads to obesity

Crosstab					
Count					
		Does taking some medications lead to obesity?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	
Does thyroid gland	Yes	36	1	2	39

secretion affect weight?	No	0	0	1	1
	To some extent	10	0	0	10
Total		46	1	3	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	16.648 ^a	4	.002
Likelihood Ratio	7.404	4	.116
Linear-by-Linear Association	.112	1	.738
N of Valid Cases	50		

a. 7 cells (77.8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02.

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between the effect of thyroid secretion on weight and taking some medications that lead to obesity: H₀

- There is a significant relationship between the effect of thyroid secretion on weight and taking some medications that lead to obesity: H₁

It is clear to us from Table No. (14) that the Chi-Square value reached (0.002) which is less than the significance level (0.05) and accordingly we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis

Table No. (15) shows the relationship between obesity that increases the chance of gallstones and liver and kidney problems and the genetic factor is one of the most important reasons that cause obesity in humans

Crosstab					
Count					
		Is genetics one of the most important reasons that cause obesity in humans?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	
Do you think obesity increases the risk of gallstones and liver and kidney problems?	Yes	6	4	7	17
	No	8	1	1	10
	To some extent	4	7	12	23
Total		18	12	20	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.916 ^a	4	.018
Likelihood Ratio	12.144	4	.016
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.503	1	.220
N of Valid Cases	50		

a. 4 cells (44.4%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.40.

Hypothesis

H0: -There is no significant relationship between obesity, which increases the chance of gallstones, liver and kidney problems, and genetic factors are among the most important causes of obesity in humans

H1: -There is a significant relationship between obesity, which increases the chance of gallstones, liver and kidney problems, and genetic factors are among the most important causes of obesity in humans

It is clear to us from Table No. (15) that the Chi-Square value reached (0.018), which is less than the significance level (0.05), and accordingly we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis

Table No. (16) shows the relationship between obesity leading to problems in the joints, skeletal and muscular systems, and in your opinion, obesity increases the risk of developing certain types of cancer

Crosstab					
Count					
		In your opinion, does obesity increase the risk of developing certain types of cancer?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	
Obesity leads to problems in the joints, skeletal and muscular systems?	Yes	11	18	17	46
	No	0	0	1	1
	To some extent	0	1	2	3
Total		11	19	20	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.909 ^a	4	.573
Likelihood Ratio	3.813	4	.432
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.941	1	.164
N of Valid Cases	50		
a. 6 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .22.			

Hypothesis

H0: - There is no significant relationship between obesity leading to problems in the joints and the skeletal and muscular system, and in your opinion, obesity increases the risk of developing certain types of cancer

H1: -There is a significant relationship between obesity leading to problems in the joints and the skeletal and muscular system, and in your opinion, obesity increases the risk of developing certain types of cancer

It is clear to us from Table No. (16) that the Chi-Square value reached (0.573), which is greater than the significance level (0.05), and accordingly we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis

Table No. (17) shows the relationship between taking some medications leading to obesity and lack of sleep can have a negative effect on weight

Crosstab					
Count					
		Can lack of sleep have a negative effect on body weight?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	
Do you think that taking some medications leads to obesity?	Yes	8	5	12	25
	No	2	3	1	6
	To some extent	8	4	7	19
Total		18	12	20	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.509 ^a	4	.476
Likelihood Ratio	3.320	4	.506
Linear-by-Linear Association	.676	1	.411
N of Valid Cases	50		

a. 4 cells (44.4%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.44.

Hypothesis

H0: -There is no significant relationship between taking some medications that lead to obesity and lack of sleep can have a negative effect on weight

H1: -There is a significant relationship between taking some medications that lead to obesity and lack of sleep can have a negative effect on weight

It is clear to us from Table No. (17) that the Chi-Square value reached (0.476) which is greater than the significance level (0.05) and accordingly we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis

Table No. (18) shows the relationship between eating healthy food, one of the most important ways to prevent obesity, and lack of sleep can have a negative effect on weight

Crosstab					
Count					
		Can lack of sleep have a negative effect on body weight?			Total
		Yes	No	To some extent	
Is eating healthy food one of the most important ways to prevent obesity?	Yes	13	8	15	36
	No	2	0	1	3
	To some extent	3	4	4	11
Total		18	12	20	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.579 ^a	4	.631
Likelihood Ratio	3.069	4	.546
Linear-by-Linear Association	.000	1	1.000
N of Valid Cases	50		
a. 6 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .72.			

Hypothesis

H0: -There is no significant relationship between eating healthy food, one of the most important ways to prevent obesity, and lack of sleep, which can have a negative effect on weight

H1: -There is a significant relationship between eating healthy food, one of the most important ways to prevent obesity, and lack of sleep, which can have a negative effect on weight

It is clear from Table (18) that the Chi-Square value reached (0.631), which is greater than the significance level (0.05), and accordingly we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis

Conclusions

After the questionnaire forms were distributed to a sample of the community (males and females), which amounted to (50) samples, we entered the answers and sorted them through the statistical program (SPSS) and obtained several conclusions that we summarize in several points as follows:

- A percentage of (0.016) was obtained for the Chi-Square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), which means that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena, gender and thyroid secretion on weight, as Shown in Table No.(4) .
- A percentage of (40.00) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), which means that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena: academic achievement and obesity leading to joint, skeletal and muscular problems, as shown in Table No.(5) .
- A percentage of (0.007) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), which means that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena: academic achievement and absence or lack of exercise, as shown in Table No.(6) .
- A percentage of (0.006) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), which means that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena: suffering from obesity and believing that childhood obesity means lifelong obesity, as shown in Table No.(7) .
- A percentage of (0.046) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), meaning that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena: suffering from obesity and having diabetes, which is one of the harms of marital obesity, as shown in Table No .(8)
- A percentage of (0.013) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), meaning that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena: the obese person is exposed to a number of serious health problems, and the absence or lack of exercise leads to obesity, as shown in Table No.(9) .
- A percentage of (0.013) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), meaning that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena: serious health

problems and frequent consumption of processed foods, sugars and starches on obesity, as shown in Table No.(10) .

- A percentage of (0.002) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), which means that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena: eating healthy food and thyroid secretion on weight, as shown in Table No.(11) .
- A percentage of (0.044) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), which means that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena: the genetic factor causing obesity and lack of sleep on weight, as shown in Table No.(12) .
- A percentage of (0.036) was obtained for the Chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), which means that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena: the effect of obesity on a person's psychological state and social life, and that the obese person is exposed to a number of health problems, as shown in Table No.(13) .
- A percentage of (0.002) was obtained for the chi-square value, which is smaller than the significance level (0.05), and this means that there is a significant relationship between the two phenomena: the effect of thyroid secretion on weight and taking some medications leads to obesity, as shown in Table No.(14) .

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